

Project Description

1. Vision for a research centered pilot project (SCC-CIVIC-PG Track B proposal)

Our project vision, developed from a request for assistance in March 2020 from the City of Atlantic Beach, is to reduce flooding risk from storm wave surge by the ecological engineering of our estuary (while safeguarding ecological integrity), and to substantially strengthen community preparedness and resiliency to this risk. By community we mean the residents in Atlantic Beach, Florida with special focus on residents in a low to moderate income area bordering our estuary including the new Habitat for Humanity residential housing development. This low-lying area is highly vulnerable to flooding from storm surge and waves due its proximity to the estuary and flat topography (City of Atlantic Beach, 2020; Hansell and Gold, 2019). Our pilot research program on optimizing the hazard mitigation properties of our estuary will create new opportunities for community learning through participation. Our children will learn about the estuary

Figure 1: Community preparedness and resiliency to be strengthened through a comprehensive outreach project implemented by a dedicated multi-disciplinary team of professionals from the nonprofit Tidal Marsh Program, City of Atlantic Beach, and the University of North Florida. This integrated graphic briefly describes, (a) the low to moderate income (LMI) area (magenta line, defined by US Census Tract 139.02) located immediately east of the estuary (geographic coordinates shown) within the City of Atlantic Beach, and (b) a preliminary six phase programmatic workplan has been conceptualized to guide the project team into Stage 2 planning, and (c) our plan for project planning and outreach, team solidification, a research pilot design, and during the four month Stage 1 Planning Grant (PG) period. Complete details with implementation schedule and personnel assignments are included in this Stage 1 PG proposal.

developed materials, and hands-on participation in the pilot research project. A complete description of education programs and materials will be included in the Stage 2 (Full Award [FA]) proposal. Through the course of co-operating and communicating to perform the pilot research, new professional relationships will be created, new lines of communication established and new knowledge and understanding realized of how effectively public-private-university can work together to respond to municipal needs.

Our Principal Investigator (PI) is Gary D. Moore, a resident of Atlantic Beach, Florida and founder of the nonprofit Tidal Marsh Program, a grassroots organization that supports the City of Atlantic Beach in its hazard mitigation, resiliency, and adaptation planning. Working closely with Gary will be Steve Swann, PE, City Engineer for the City of Atlantic Beach. Gary and Steve will be responsible for communicating the Project’s vision, goals, and objective by developing, describing and programmatic workplan with emphasis on community and public school outreach programs. Supporting the PI are scientists from the University of North Florida (UNF). Christopher J. Brown, PhD, P.E. is Professor of civil engineering who will assist with the development of community engagement plans, design of the pilot research, and integration with the pioneering UNF-led regional water resource management modeling for the St. Johns River basin including the Intracoastal Waterway adjacent to Atlantic Beach and its estuaries and tributaries. Dr. Brown is the coordinator for the senior Capstone program for engineering students. O. Patrick Kreidl, PhD is Associate Professor of electrical engineering at UNF and will assist with the development of plans to engage the community, and design of the pilot research project. Kelly J. Smith, PhD (co-PI) is Associate Professor of biology in the Coastal and Marine Biology Program at UNF. Dr. Smith will assist to develop community engagement plans, and provide expertise in estuarine systems. The nonprofit Tidal Marsh Program, in collaboration with the Engineering Department of the city of Atlantic Beach is responsible for planning and conducting community and public school outreach, finalization of the project’s vision, goal(s), the programmatic workplan and the pilot research project. The UNF team members are responsible for assisting in community and public schools outreach, and design of the pilot research project, ensuring the design is of the highest quality, credible, and protective of the ecosystem.

1.1 Activities, plans, schedule

Our Stage 1 PG work is planned to be implemented in the four major tasks as illustrated across the top of Figure 2 with a schedule presented in Figure 3. Task activities in the Stage 1 PG, with emphasis on extensive community outreach, are designed to form the core basis of the Stage 2 Full Award proposal. The tasks are: 1) Strengthen collaboration with stakeholders, 2) Solidifying academic and civic partners, 3) Stage 2 FA proposal preparation, 4) Engage in Community of Practice capacity building events.

Figure 2: Personnel assignments according to task and expertise for work on the Stage 1 Planning Grant.

Figure 3: A schedule of tasks (Gantt Chart) has been prepared to guide the team during the Stage 1 PG period.

The schedule of major tasks and intermediate activities has been prepared. **Task 1: Strengthen collaboration with stakeholders** planned is heavily weighted on performing community outreach at the outset of Stage 1 PG period. This is important because our approach is to gather extensive community information and feedback to shape the planning of the Stage 2 FA workplan and proposal. Several neighborhoods, numerous small businesses, at least two nonprofit organizations (focused on providing services to low income residents in need of housing), and two public schools are located in or near the project area. As practicable, each of these will be contacted about the project and asked to contribute ideas for extending our outreach to the most vulnerable residents to inform project planning. In addition, two site visits are planned. **Task 2: Solidifying academic and civic partner roles** is organized to bring the team together to openly communicate ideas and strategies for project planning and personnel assignments. Through these communication sessions the role(s) for each team member for the Stage 2 FA work planning will be finalized. **Task 3: Stage 2 proposal preparation and submittal** will involve intensive multi-step work to develop the representative documents and graphics to effectively express our plans to achieve our vision. Finally for Stage 1 PG period, **Task 4: Community-of-Practice activities** we will actively participate in the capacity building activities, webinars, project calls, and showcase. It is planned that our

the nonprofit organization will attend the Washington, D.C. sessions accompanied by one member from UNF.

A preliminary programmatic workplan has been developed that gives organizational structure to the many tasks that must be performed for this project. The preliminary programmatic workplan consists of six phases which are briefly described below:

- Phase 1 (*Stage 1 – Planning Grant*) – Phase I of the programmatic workplan describes all activities to be performed during the Stage 1 PG four month period.
- Phases 2-6 (*Stage 2 – Full Award Grant*) – These phases describe implementation of the full award including community and school outreach for project integration, pilot research, data analysis, mapping, and reporting, and capacity building for the City of Atlantic Beach. Our pilot research is the optimization of coastal marsh ‘buffers’ in storm wave surge mitigation and community preparedness.

Phase 1 of the programmatic workplan

Phase 1 (*Stage 1 PG period*) activities to be performed during Phase 1 of the programmatic workplan are primarily focused on initial community outreach, team strengthening, and project planning. The following specific activities will be performed:

- Conduct weekly (teleconference) planning meetings with team members;
- Brainstorming creative approaches to community outreach and integration of stakeholders;
- Conduct four community and school outreach events to strengthen collaborations with stakeholders, communicate program details and receive feedback;
- Conduct two site visits to familiarize our team with the complexities of our estuary;
- Strengthening relationships among the team, civic partners, and community and school stakeholders;
- Finalizing the plan for pilot research project and integration of community and school stakeholders;
- Communicate program details to the community through a variety of existing media channels;
- Finalize scope of phases 2 through 6 of the programmatic workplan;
- Participate in Community-of-Practice activities; and,
- Prepare to submit a proposal for Stage 2 (FA) (*invited*), inclusive of all information as required in the Program Solicitation NSF 20-562.

Success of the Stage 1 PG period activities will be measured, documented, and reported. In addition, to ensure the project is effectively communicating with the community, programs will be updated and improved after each event as feedback is received. Specific details on how the performance and effectiveness measurements will be performed, the methodologies to be used will be described in the Stage 2 (FA) proposal.

1.2 Research questions

Our social science and technical questions during the PG period are described below:

Social science and technical questions:

- How do we effectively engage our community stakeholders (residents and organizations) and public schools in outreach and involvement activities to share knowledge about the importance of (the hazard mitigation capabilities) of our marsh, and the health of the marsh in general?
- What strategies do we use to ensure deep engagement with the residents and nonprofit organizations located in or near the low to moderate income areas adjacent to the marsh?

- What is our technical and scientific plan for pilot investigation in marsh optimization for hazard mitigation by our integrated multidisciplinary team?

Knowledge gaps

- How to optimize the storm wave surge mitigation capabilities of a marsh while safeguarding the estuary's integrity?

1.3 Intellectual merit

It is widely acknowledged in the US and abroad that coastal marsh 'buffer areas' can reduce the damaging effects of storm wave surge. However, this acknowledged understanding is intuitive, limited in usefulness because it is mostly *qualitative*. Our investigation seeks to advance the ways in which natural coastal estuaries could be used or re-designed/restored by exploring how these natural ecosystems can be *quantified*. Once quantified they can be included explicitly in predictive models for community hazard assessment and disaster preparedness. In addition, once quantified the possibility of modifying the system to maximize its usefulness (optimization) for storm surge wave reduction is created. Regarding *quantification* of typical marsh plants and marsh ecosystems, the background basic research on typical marsh flora characteristics for wave energy mitigation and resiliency has been published by others (US Army, 2011; Moller et al., 2014, Feagin et al., 2011, Cheong et al., 2013). We consider these marsh buffer areas as potential *tools* to be modified and optimized and utilized for coastal community in storm hazard preparedness and defense.

2. Civic engagement

2.1 Community participants and collaborative approach

To make an initial announcement and invitation regarding the PG to community stakeholders, the team will leverage existing communication channels developed by the City of Atlantic Beach. Those channels consist of a municipal web site, monthly newsletter flyer distributed with the utility bill, and networking with the City Commissioner (elected by residents in west Atlantic Beach) to reach community leaders among the residents. For the Stage 1 PG period ongoing information distribution may continue with these channels but in addition the nonprofit Tidal Marsh Program website can function as both a source of information update and a place for interested community members and organizations to make unilateral contact (encouraged) with the team. To assist the team in the project, a student engineering team, participating in the UNF Senior Capstone program, will be invited to be involved in all aspects of project engagement For Stage 2 FA new communications and information sharing channels will be established, channels such as Twitter, Facebook, dedicated project website with email, blog, and news update capabilities.

Our collaborative approach will be governed by openness, equity, and inclusiveness with a community first philosophy. Technically we will be informed by the substantial social and physiological literature on civic engagement and guidance documents published by authoritative sources, for example, *Principles of Community Engagement* (NIH, 2011). We have found recent information on modern, practical strategies for community engagement and ongoing communication in the current environment of COVID-19 to be especially interesting and idea producing (Smith Group, 2020). Our team has the technical and schedule capacity to undertake this project.

2.2 Community perspective of project significance

During the Stage 1 PG period we will diligently seek answers to questions such as, How do we feature residents' value of the marsh?, What is the city's value of research?, How do we convey the benefit of research to underrepresented groups?

3. Broader Impacts

The proposed tidal marsh pilot project, developed by an integrated community-university team, aims to balance action with research and innovation. It will be designed and managed to focus on immediate, tangible benefits to the community while also advancing research on the effectiveness of tidal marshes to provide storm surge resiliency. The PG itself invests significantly into fostering a robust “community of practice” among Atlantic Beach stakeholders, whose sustainment through full award will promote the project’s actionable research knowledge and its model of co-learning and capacity building to transfer to other communities at risk of storm surge and wave damage. The PG is designed to immediately advance increased literacy and public engagement by community members. The involvement of K-12 students as well as college students within the combined outreach and research efforts will also boost visibility of STEM educational/career opportunities. The pilot project itself will ultimately lead to improved flood resiliency within the Atlantic Beach community.

A rigorous, quantitative characterization of the engineering properties of the Atlantic Beach tidal marsh as concerns storm surge and hazard mitigation has value far beyond the city limits. Such fine-scale data and analyses can be leveraged within coarser-scale analytical and numerical resiliency models to more accurately account for the benefit of these natural ecological systems. The figure to the right shows the proposed pilot project area (red dot) within the spatial boundaries (in black) of the entire St. John’s watershed, including the Atlantic coast, for which UNF is already developing an integrated hydrodynamic model that the tidal marsh study can directly inform. This tool, that can help a larger region understand flood resiliency, will be improved by data exchange with the pilot project. In addition, university students from multiple disciplines will support this project; during the PG itself, the team will utilize undergraduate civil engineering students and graduate biology students to help plan the pilot and collect baseline data.

4. Results from Prior NSF Support

Neither Gary Moore (PI), Kelly Smith (co-PI) nor Christopher Brown (Key Personnel) have received prior NSF support. Patrick Kreidl (Key Personnel) is a co-PI under recent NSF Award 1932300 in the amount of \$364,721 for the period 03/01/2020 to 02/28/2023 and titled *CPS: Small: Collaborative Research: RUI: Towards Efficient and Secure Agricultural Information Collection Using a Multi-Robot System*. A collaboration between the University of North Florida (UNF) and the University of Central Florida (UCF), the project’s major goals are to (i) train students to conduct basic and applied research while closely working with local farmland partners in northeast Florida and (ii) develop and implement novel information collection techniques for autonomous mobile robots that collect, store and share data in an efficient yet secure manner. The project’s broader impacts include (i) alignment with an established Memorandum of Understanding between UNF and UCF to provide a conduit for engineering/computing students to pursue M.S. degrees at UNF that feed seamlessly into Ph.D. programs at UCF and (ii) to raise awareness among today's teenagers and young adults of the impending agricultural crisis if worldwide food production falls even further behind meeting demands of an increasing global population.

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